

A Study of the Complex Compounds of *N*-Benzenesulphonyl Glycine with Some Metal Ions

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The compound, *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycine (RH_2), forms complex compounds with Cu, Ag, Zn, Cd, and Hg and behaves as both monoprotic and biprotic bidentate ligand. The compounds isolated in the pure state are of the types: $M^{II}(RH)(OH)(H_2O)$, $M^{II}(RH)_2$, and $M_2^{II}M^{II}R_2$ (where $M^{II} = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}$, or Hg^{II} and $M^I = Na^+$, K^+ , or Ba^{2+}). Silver compounds isolated are of the types: M^+AgR and $Ag(RH)$. The dissociation constants of the ligand and the complex acids as well as stability constants of the complexes in 1:1 aqueous ethanolic solution have been determined by pH measurement, following the method of Bjerrum, and the stability order found are: $Cu > Zn > Cd$. The light blue copper mono-compound $[Cu(RH)(OH)(H_2O)]H_2O$ on heating at 110° for 2½ hours changes colour to green with loss of two molecules of water per mole of the complex and forms a slow-

reacting insoluble copper compound, probably having a diol bridge structure as $RHCu$

Sulphonamides have been found to react with metal ions to provide complex compounds. The most common sulphonamide, sulphanilamide¹, forms complex compounds with copper sulphate as also prontosil¹. The compound, mono-*p*-toluenesulphonyl derivative of *o*-phenylenediamine, affords a green chelate with $Cu(II)$ and has been shown to be a specific reagent for the estimation of copper². Kachhwaha and Gaur³ from potentiometric study obtained an indication of a 2:1 complex of *p*-toluenesulphonyl glycine with $Cu(II)$ and pointed out that the ligand acted as a biprotic bidentate.

N-Benzenesulphonyl glycine has been found to behave as both monoprotic and biprotic bidentate ligand and forms complex compounds with $Cu(II)$, $Zn(II)$, $Cd(II)$, $Hg(II)$, and $Ag(I)$. In view of the fact that the sulphonamides are potentially useful in analytical chemistry and scanty work seems to have been done on their complex formation reactions, the isolation of the complex compounds in the pure state, investigation into their mechanism of formations and a study on their stabilities have been undertaken.

The compound, *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycine (RH_2), has been found to form the following compounds: $M^{II}(RH)(OH)(H_2O)$, $M^{II}(RH)_2$, and $M_2^{II}M^{II}R_2$, where $M^{II} = Cu(II)$, $Zn(II)$, $Cd(II)$, and $Hg(II)$ and $M^I = Na^+$, K^+ , and Ba^{2+} , and the silver compound: $KAgR$ and $Ag(RH)$. The light blue copper compound, $[Cu(RH)(OH)(H_2O)]H_2O$, on heating

1. Macarovic, *Bul. Soc. Stiinte Cluj*, 1940, 9, 426.
2. Billman et al., *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 1342.
3. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 399.

changes to a green, insoluble one which appears to involve the following reversible change:

The dissociation constants of the ligand and the complex acid and the stability constants of these complexes were determined by *pH*-titrations, following the method of Bjerrum⁴. The reagent RH_2 is a weak acid; its dissociation may be represented by

and the dissociation constant K^* is given by

$$K^* = \frac{[\text{RH}^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{RH}_2]}$$

This constant is determined by measuring the *pH* values of the solutions resulting from progressive addition of a standard alkali to a reagent solution of known strength and from the formation curve, obtained by plotting η_{H} against *pH* values [where η_{H} = average number of H^+ ion attached to ligand ion (RH^-):

$$\eta_{\text{H}} = \frac{\text{Total No. of } \text{H}^+ \text{ bound to } \text{RH}^-}{\text{Total No. of ligand mol. present}} = \frac{\text{RH}_2}{\text{RH}^- + \text{RH}_2} = \frac{\text{R} - \text{P} - \text{H}^+ + \text{OH}^-}{\text{R}}$$

where R = total concentration of the reagent and P = the concentration of alkali added. The correct value of pK^* is obtained from the curve as *pH* when $\eta_{\text{H}} = 1/2$.

Now the values of formation constants have been determined in the following manner. When a mixture of metal nitrate, containing some free HNO_3 and an excess of RH_2 in 50% aqueous ethanol (v/v), is treated with increasing amounts of a standard alkali, the *pH* gradually rises and the metal ion takes up 1, 2, etc. molecules of the ligand to form complex compounds. The formation of the complex compound between RH_2 and metal ions may be assumed to take place in successive stages:

The equilibrium constants of the above reactions may therefore be given by

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{M}(\text{RH})^+][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{M}^{2+}][\text{RH}_2]}$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{M}(\text{RH})_2][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{M}(\text{RH})^+][\text{RH}_2]}$$

These constants are determined by measuring *pH* values of the solutions resulting from progressive addition of alkali to a mixture of $\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and RH_2 solutions containing

4. "Metalamine Formation in Aqueous Solutions", P. Haas and Soes, Copenhagen, 1941.

free HNO_3 . Further addition of alkali results in the neutralisation of the complex acids, $[\text{M}(\text{RH})_2]^-$, represented by

and let K_3 and K_4 represent the respective dissociation constants.

If η_f be the average number of ligands attached per metal ion, then

$$\eta_f = \frac{M_1 + 2M_2 + 2M^1 + 2M^{11}}{M}$$

where M = total concentration of the metal present, $M_1 = [\text{MRH}]^+$, $M_2 = [\text{MR}(\text{RH})^-]$, $M^1 = [\text{MR}(\text{RH})^-]$, and $M^{11} = [\text{MR}_2^{2-}]$.

Now, during titration the following relations hold good at any instant:

$$M = M_0 + M_1 + M_2 + M^1 + M^{11} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$R = M_1 + 2M_2 + 2M^1 + 2M^{11} + R_0 + R_1 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

and since the solutions are electrically neutral,

$$2M_0 + M_1 + \text{H}^+ + P = M^1 + 2M^{11} + R_1 + \text{OH}^- + F + 2M \quad (3)$$

where M_0 = concentration of free metal ions, R = total concentration of the reagent RH_2 , P = concentration of alkali added, F = concentration of free acid, $R_1 = [\text{RH}^-]$ and $R_0 = [\text{RH}_2]$.

From relations (1), (2), and (3) one may obtain

$$R_0 = R - (P + \text{H}^+ - \text{OH}^- - F - M^1 - 2M^{11}) \quad (4)$$

$$\eta_f = \frac{R - R_0 - R_1}{M} = \frac{R - R_0 \{1 + (K^0/[\text{H}^+])\}}{M} \quad (5)$$

So long the complex formation takes place, M^1 and M^{11} may be regarded as small. Now, by plotting the values of η_f against $(p\text{H} + \log R_0)$, the formation curve is obtained from which the values of $(p\text{H} + \log R_0)$, when $\eta_f = 1/2$ and $3/2$, may be extrapolated. The correct values of K_1 and K_2 may then be calculated from the following equations:

$$K_1 = b\eta_f = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{3K_2}} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

$$K_2 = b\eta_f = \frac{3}{1 + \frac{3}{K_1}} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where $p(b) = p\text{H} + \log R_0$. The successive stability constants are calculated from the relations $k_1 = K_1/K^0$ and $k_2 = K_2/K^0$.

The dissociation constants of the complex acids are obtained as follows. When

neutralisation of $[M(RH)_n]$ begins, M_0 and M_n present may be regarded as negligible. Therefore

$$R = 2M + R_0 + R_1 \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

$$P + H^+ = 2M + F + R_1 + M' + 2M'' + OH^- \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

From equations (8) and (9)

$$R_1 = \frac{R - 2M}{1 + ([H^+]/K^*)} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

and $\eta_H =$ average number of H^+ ions bound to complex ion M''

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{2M - (M' + 2M'')}{M} \\ &= 4 - \frac{(P + H^+ - F - OH^-) - R_1}{M} \quad \dots \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

The values of η_H are plotted against the corresponding pH values and from the curve, approximate values of pK_3 and pK_4 are obtained as pH , when $\eta_H = 3/2$ and $1/2$ respectively. The correct values may then be calculated from the following equations:

$$K_3 = [H^+] \eta_{H=3/2} \left(1 + \frac{3[H^+] \eta_{H=3/2}}{K_4} \right) \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

$$K_4 = [H^+] \eta_{H=1/2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{[H^+] \eta_{H=1/2}}{3K_3}} \right) \quad (13)$$

During determination of the values of K_3 and K_4 in the cases of Zn and Cd, when η_H is near about 0.5, the complex compounds begin to decompose with precipitation of the respective oxides, suggesting that the pure alkali metal compound containing the complex ion, $[M R_n]^{2-}$ ($M = Zn^{2+}$ or Cd^{2+}), cannot be prepared from the solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Benzenesulphonyl glycine was prepared by the usual method⁵ of interaction of glycine and benzenesulphonyl chloride in presence of alkali. It was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 165-66°. (Found: Equiv., 215.4. Calc., 215). It is soluble in acetone, ethanol, dioxane, hot water, etc. and sparingly soluble in cold water, ether, benzene, toluene, etc.

A. Complex Compounds of Copper (II)

(1). $[Cu(RH)(OH)(H_2O)]$.—Freshly prepared CuO in aqueous suspension was treated with RH_2 in acetone solution in the ratio of 1:1. The mixture was thoroughly shaken in a stoppered bottle and heated on a water bath, when CuO dissolved, forming a blue solu-

tion. It was filtered and the filtrate was allowed to cool and evaporate in air. After several hours, light blue crystals separating were collected, thoroughly washed with acetone, and air-dried. [Found: Cu, 19.31; N, 4.40. $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 19.23; N, 4.24%]. This compound on keeping in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 for several days lost one molecule of water (loss found, 5.41; calc. 5.44%) and on heating at 110° for 24 hours lost two molecules of water, yielding a green, insoluble, slow-reacting compound, possibly having the diol bridge. (Found: Cu, 21.46; N, 4.83. Formula requires Cu, 21.58; N, 4.75%).

(2). $[\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2]$ and $\text{M}'_2[\text{CuR}_2]$ ($\text{M}' = \text{Na}^+$ or $\frac{1}{2}\text{Ba}^{++}$).—Freshly precipitated CuO, treated with RH_2 in ethanol (in the ratio 1:2), was refluxed on a steam bath for 15 hours. It was then cooled and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated on a water bath and finally in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . The blue powder obtained was washed several times with redistilled acetone. [Found: Cu, 12.85; N, 5.71. $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2$ requires Cu, 12.90; N, 5.69%].

An aqueous suspension of CuO was heated on the water bath with an aqueous solution of NaRH (in the ratio 1:2) till CuO dissolved. It was filtered and the filtrate was allowed to evaporate in air when deep blue crystals were obtained. It was dried in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 . (Found: Cu, 11.79; N, 5.31; Na, 8.52. Na_2CuR_2 requires Cu, 11.87; N, 5.23; Na, 8.59%).

Barium salt was obtained as a crystalline precipitate when an aqueous solution of Na_2CuR_2 was treated with the requisite amount of $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution. It was dried over H_2SO_4 . (Found: Cu, 10.10; N, 4.42; Ba, 22.02. BaCuR_2 requires Cu, 10.14; N, 4.47; Ba, 21.86%).

B. Complex Compounds of Silver (1).—Freshly precipitated Ag_2O and RH_2 in ethanolic solution in the ratio 1:2 were shaken together for 3 to 4 days and filtered. The residue was washed with acetone and air-dried. [Found: Ag, 33.12; N, 4.45. $\text{Ag}(\text{RH})$ requires Ag, 33.54; N, 4.35%].

Sodium salt, prepared as the copper compound, could not be crystallised. It formed a glassy material. The *potassium salt* was obtained as a crystalline compound. (Found: Ag, 29.83; K, 10.62. KAgR requires Ag, 29.99; K, 10.83%).

C. Complex Compounds of Zinc.—Only one complex compound of zinc was isolated by following the procedure for the preparation of $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2$. [Found: Zn, 13.10; N, 5.74. $\text{Zn}(\text{RH})_2$ requires Zn, 13.25; N, 5.68%].

D. Complex Compounds of Cadmium.—The mono-compound was prepared as a white crystalline solid (dried in a desiccator over H_2SO_4), following the procedure for the corresponding Cu-compound. [Found: Cd, 31.00; N, 3.98. $\text{Cd}(\text{RH})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ requires Cd, 31.10; N, 3.87%]. The bis-compound was prepared by shaking and warming a mixture of CdO and RH_2 (in the ratio 1:2.5) in aqueous suspension. The clear solution was allowed to evaporate in air when crystals separated. These were collected, thoroughly washed with redistilled acetone, and dried in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 . [Found: Cd, 20.52; N, 5.22. $\text{Cd}(\text{RH})_2$ requires Cd, 20.80; N, 5.18%].

F. Complex Compounds of Mercury.—Methods of their preparation were the same as for Cu-complexes except with the bis-compound of mercury, where $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution, slightly acidified with HNO_3 , was allowed to react with RH_2 (in the ratio 1:2) and the pH was raised to 3 to 4 with dilute NaOH solution. A white crystalline precipitate separated which was collected and washed with water and acetone. It was dried in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 . The analyses of the complexes are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound.	%Hg		% N		% M ⁺	
	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
$\text{Hg}(\text{RH})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	44.91	44.62	3.32	3.12		
$\text{Hg}(\text{RH})_2$	32.02	31.91	4.57	4.45		
K_2HgR_2	28.18	28.46	..	..	10.92	11.07
BaHgR_2	26.02	26.27	3.71	3.67	18.10	17.38

Sodium salt was prepared and found to be glassy.

Determination of Formation and Dissociation Constants

Solid KOH (A. R. quality) (60 g.) after washing with a small quantity of water was dissolved and diluted with double distilled water to one litre. The solution was standardised with hydrazine sulphate. Dehydrated ethanol (1.5 litres) was taken in a flask and refluxed for 8 to 10 hours with calcium metal (8 g.) and then distilled.

The reagent RH_2 was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. Other reagents used were of A.R. quality. All pH-measurements were made in 50% aqueous-ethanol (v/v) at the room temperature (30°) with a Cambridge portable type pH-meter.

Acid Dissociation Constant of the Reagent (RH_2).—A solution of RH_2 (0.05245 M, 50 ml) was titrated with a 0.5855 M-KOH solution in 50% aqueous-ethanol. The resulting pH values were noted and η_{H} values were calculated (Table II). The results (η_{H} vs. pH) were plotted as shown in Fig. 2. pK^* was determined from the curve by extrapolation and found to be 4.50, being equal to pH, when $\eta_{\text{H}}=1/2$.

TABLE II

Alkali added.	pH.	η_{H} .	Alkali added.	pH.	η_{H} .
0.0 ml	2.96	0.96	2.4 ml	4.54	0.47
0.4	3.42	0.90	2.8	4.68	0.37
0.8	3.72	0.81	3.2	4.84	0.28
1.2	4.03	0.73	3.6	5.05	0.18
1.6	4.25	0.64	4.0	5.50	0.11
2.0	4.40	0.55	4.4	7.50	0.01

Determination of Formation Constants K_1 and K_2 of Complexes.—Solutions (each 50 ml) containing 0.01 M- $\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, 0.05245 M- R.H_2 , and 0.01 M free HNO_3 were titrated with 0.5855 M-KOH solution and the pH values were noted (Table III). η_{H} values were calculated, using equation (5), and plotted against $p(b)$, as shown in Fig. 1. The constant values of pK_1 and pK_2 were calculated with the help of equations (6) and (7) and the

successive stability constants k_1 and k_2 were then calculated as K_1/K^* and K_2/K^* respectively. The results are recorded in Table IV.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

TABLE III

Alkali added.	pH values.			Alkali added.	pH values.		
	Cu.	Zn.	Cd.		Cu.	Zn.	Cd.
0.0 ml	2.20	2.22	2.23	4.4 ml	4.42	4.86	4.84
0.4	2.41	2.46	2.47	4.8	4.52	5.01	4.98
0.8	2.55	2.63	2.66	4.8	4.61	5.17	5.16
1.0	2.82	3.08	3.10	5.0	4.72	5.41	5.39
1.2	2.95	3.26	3.29	5.2	4.87	5.78	5.86
1.4	3.08	3.40	3.44	5.4	5.03	6.09	6.54
1.6	3.20	3.63	3.56	5.5	..	6.21	6.81
1.8	3.29	3.64	3.67	5.6	5.25	6.39	7.03
2.0	3.40	3.75	3.77	5.7	..	6.50	7.23
2.2	3.49	3.85	3.87	5.8	5.59	6.68	7.38
2.4	3.57	3.93	3.98	5.9	..	6.81	7.56
2.6	3.68	4.03	4.06	6.0	6.24	6.96	7.76
2.8	3.74	4.11	4.13	6.1	..	7.13	7.95
3.0	3.83	4.18	4.20	6.2	6.80	7.26	8.14
3.2	3.91	4.26	4.28	6.3	..	7.39	8.34
3.4	4.00	4.34	4.36	6.4	7.20	7.56	8.52
3.6	4.08	4.43	4.45	6.5	..	7.72	8.72
3.8	4.15	4.53	4.54	6.6	7.65	7.88	8.87
4.0	4.24	4.63	4.63	6.8	8.25	..	..
4.2	4.32	4.74	4.72	6.9	9.40	..	..

Acid Dissociation Constants of the Complex Acid $M(RH)_2$.—In the above titrations, as shown in Table III, the values of η_H were calculated from the corresponding pH values, using equation (11). These values were plotted against pH values, as shown in Fig. 2, and from the curve, the correct values of pK_3 and pK_4 were calculated, using equations (12) and (13). The results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Metal ion.	pK_1 .	pK_2 .	Log k_1 .	Log k_2 .	pK_3 .	pK_4 .
Cu ²⁺	2.64	1.10	1.86	3.40	4.19	7.70
Zn ²⁺	2.03	1.97	1.57	2.53	6.61	7.88
Cd ²⁺	3.27	1.72	1.23	2.77	7.28	8.89

The final acid concentration was determined as follows. A known quantity of HNO₃ in 50% aqueous ethanol was titrated with a standard alkali in 50% aqueous ethanol and pH values were noted. The final acid concentrations were extrapolated from the corresponding pH.

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Received April 11, 1963.